

Synthetic approaches to cyclophanes via Claisen rearrangement and ring-closing metathesis as key steps

Sambasivarao Kotha*, Arjun S. Chavan and Gopalkrushna T. Waghule

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai-400 076, India

E-mail : srk@chem.iitb.ac.in

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Abstract : Claisen rearrangement and ring-closing metathesis combination is finding its way in designing intricate targets. We have assembled cyclophanes via Claisen rearrangement, and ring-closing metathesis as key steps.

Keywords : Claisen rearrangement, allylation, ring-closing metathesis, cyclophane, template reaction.

Introduction

Since the discovery of cyclophanes, interesting strategies have been reported to generate these intricate molecules. Heterophanes, another subclass of cyclophane, possesses biological activities such as antimicrobial¹, anti-inflammatory², and antifungal³. Diverse applications of cyclophanes in host-guest chemistry, molecular recognition aspect, charge-transfer studies, design of transistors, and sensors fueled the growth of these targets. Several natural products contain cyclophane as a core structural unit⁴. Among other popular reactions employed to prepare cyclophanes, Claisen rearrangement find its unique place. Also, application of ring-closing metathesis (RCM) to generate different macrocycles is well known. Due to efficiency of these reactions, they can be used to construct diverse macrocycles. Recently, sequential application of Claisen rearrangement followed by RCM have been used to generate various cyclophane derivatives⁵. Several variations of Claisen rearrangement under different reaction conditions are also reported. These include : use of Lewis acids, base, water, microwave condition, transition metal complexes, and ionic liquids. In continuation of our efforts⁶ to design various macrocycles, we conceived tandem Claisen rearrangement (TCR)⁷, double Claisen rearrangement (DCR)⁸ and RCM as key steps to assemble a library of cyclophane derivatives.

Results and discussion

The first strategy explored here involves TCR followed by RCM to generate the cyclophane ring system.

Whereas, the second strategy rely on cross-metathesis (CM) followed by TCR to deliver diverse cyclophane derivatives (Fig. 1)⁹. Third strategy consists of DCR followed by RCM to generate cyclophanes.

To begin with, 1,1-bis-(4-methyl-2-allylphenoxy-methyl)ethylene (**2a**), a precursor for the cyclophane derivative, was prepared starting with 2-allyl-4-methylphenol (**1a**)¹⁰ and 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)-1-propene using K_2CO_3 in acetone reflux conditions in 84% yield (Scheme 1). All our attempts to generate compound **2a** and **2b** under NaH/DMF conditions were not successful. Later, the compound **2** was subjected to TCR at 160–180 °C for 6 h under neat reaction conditions to isolate the rearranged product **3** in low yield (Scheme 1).

The reaction was carried out under microwave irradiation, and also using various catalyst such as $PdCl_2(PhCN)_2$, montmorillonite K-10 clay, ionic liquids in the presence of NMP or *N,N*-dimethyl aniline as a solvent. Surprisingly, all these conditions are not useful to generate the CR product. Later, the TCR of diallylated product **2b** was carried out using 2 equivalents of BCl_3 in DCM at 0 °C to deliver the rearranged product **3b** in 80% yield. Under similar reaction conditions, **2a** gave the rearranged product **3a** in poor yield along with partially rearranged product. To improve the yield, the diallylated product **2a** was subjected to TCR using 4 equivalents of BCl_3 at –60 °C¹¹. Under these conditions, **3a** was obtained in 30% yield along with the cyclized product **7** (28% yield). The formation of **7** was confirmed

Fig. 1. Retrosynthetic approach towards the cyclophane derivatives via TCR and RCM.

Reagents and conditions: (a) 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)-1-propene, K_2CO_3 , acetone, reflux;
(b) 160-180 °C, 6 h.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of precursor **3a** and **3b** for the RCM reaction.

on the basis of 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectral data and further supported by HRMS data (Scheme 2).

Compound **2a** when subjected to Claisen rearrangement in the presence of 2 equiv. of BCl_3 rearranged product **3a** was obtained. Further, addition of excess of BCl_3 causes binding of phenolic oxygen to BCl_3 while lone pair on other oxygen atom attacks on double bond (**B**) to generate five membered ring **C** which on hydrolysis with

water generated the compound **7** (Fig. 2).

All our efforts to obtain RCM product were unsuccessful, when we tried to obtain the RCM product of **3a** and its methyl ether under different metathesis catalyst conditions. We have also tried some highly reactive trifluoroacetamide-activated boomerang type ruthenium catalysts (M71-1st gen., M71SIMes, M71SIPr)¹², which are known for their utility in metathesis reaction with low

Reagents and conditions: (a) 2 equiv. BCl_3 , DCM, 0 °C - rt; (b) 4 equiv. BCl_3 , DCM, -60 °C - rt.

Scheme 2. Tandem Claisen rearrangement using BCl_3 .

Fig. 2. Proposed mechanism for the formation of rearranged product 7.

catalyst loading and short reaction period¹³. These catalysts have high stability and recyclability on a large scale for realizing RCM, enyne-metathesis (EM) and cross-metathesis (CM) reactions. The RCM protocol of compound **3** was carried out with 2 mol% of these catalysts in DCM at room temperature for 24 h, but none of these catalysts were found to be useful with our substrate, and in all our attempts we have recovered the starting material (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Attempted reactions for the synthesis of cyclophane **8** by RCM strategy.

Since our attempts to realize the RCM of **3** were unsuccessful, we intend to bring the two aromatic moieties present in the TCR product **3** in proximity by employing a template strategy¹⁴. To this end, we chose to incorporate the silicon tether using dichlorodimethylsilane as a coupling partner under basic conditions¹⁵ and the silicon containing substrate **9** was subjected to RCM¹⁶ under different reaction conditions but the desired RCM **10** was not formed. Under different metathesis catalysts reaction

conditions to generate the cyclophane derivative **10** were not successful. Later, we decided to make use of the phosphorus tether, and in this regard, the required compound **11** containing phosphorus tether was obtained by using phosphorus trichloride under basic conditions in DCM reflux¹⁷. The formation of the phosphorus containing product **11** was confirmed by ^{31}P NMR ($\delta -2.28$ ppm) and then, the RCM was attempted with G-II under toluene reflux conditions, however, the required RCM product **12** was not observed (Scheme 4).

Since several attempts to realize the RCM reaction under different catalyst and various conditions were futile. Later, we changed our strategy where the C-C bond formation sequence was changed. To this end, the two phenyl rings were connected by CM and then the TCR was planned at the end of sequence to assemble cyclophane system. To connect the two phenyl rings by CM, the 2-allyl phenol (**2**) was reacted with Grubbs catalyst. In this regard, the phenolic -OH groups were protected by iodine catalyzed acetylation using acetic anhydride¹⁸ and the acetyl product **13** was subjected to CM using G-I or G-II under DCM reflux conditions. The desired CM product **14** was obtained as a mixture of *cis-trans* isomers in good yields. Then, the CM product **14** was hydrogenated under palladium/charcoal catalyst conditions in ethyl acetate under H_2 and the hydrogenated product **15** was sub-

Reagents and conditions: (a) Me_2SiCl_2 , Et_3N , toluene, 70%; (b) PCl_3 , Et_3N , DMAP, DCM, reflux, 43%; (c) G-II, toluene, reflux; (d) G-II, toluene, reflux.

Scheme 4. Attempted RCM with silicon tether and phosphorous tether containing substrates.

jected to deacylation by potassium carbonate in methanol reflux conditions to obtain **16** with free phenolic -OH. Next, the CR precursor **17** suitable for the cyclophane derivative was prepared by the alkylation **16** with 3-chloro-(2-chloromethyl)propene-1 in the presence of sodium hydride/DMF. In case of **16b**, we have isolated the dimeric product **17b** in low yield. Later, to improve the yield of **17a** and **17b**, the alkylation reaction was attempted by varying the base (e.g. K_2CO_3 , Cs_2CO_3 , KOH, and KH) (Scheme 5).

Finally, when the compound **17b** was subjected to

TCR under BCl_3 conditions in DCM at 0°C , the unexpected product **18** was obtained in 64% yield. It appears that the cyclophane moiety formed was opened by BCl_3 during the TCR. The formation of the product **18** was confirmed by ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR. The $-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$ moiety appears at 4.00 ppm in ^1H NMR and 48.1 ppm in ^{13}C NMR spectrum. The expected cyclophane derivative **4b** was not formed. Next, the compounds **17a** and **17b** were subjected to CR under neat conditions or microwave conditions. However, under these conditions, cyclophane derivative **4b** was not obtained (Scheme 6).

Reagents and conditions : (a) acetic anhydride, iodine; (b) G- I or G-II, DCM, reflux; (c) H_2 , Pd/C, EtOAc; (d) K_2CO_3 , methanol, reflux; (e) 3-chloro-(2-chloromethyl)propene-1, NaH, DMF, 0°C - rt;

Scheme 5. Synthesis of TCR precursor **17a** and **17b**.

Reagents and conditions: (a) 2 equiv. BCl_3 , DCM, 0°C -rt, 64%.

Scheme 6. TCR of **17b** via BCl_3 .

Since both of the above routes failed to give the desired cyclophanes, we thought of increasing the chain length between two aromatic moieties and in this regard ethylene oxy linkage was considered as a viable option. Based on this concept, we devised a simple strategy for the synthesis of cyclophanes by double Claisen rearrangement (DCR) and RCM as key steps.

To generalize this strategy to other cyclophane derivatives, precursors **19** was synthesized by using a readily available starting materials such as resorcinol¹⁹. To generate more flexibility in chain length, ethylene oxy chain length was varied. Bisphenol **19** was subjected to alkylation with 3-bromoprop-1-ene to generate **20** in 90% yield. DCR of **20** gave three regio-isomeric products **21a-c** which are separated by column chromatography. These three

isomers **21a**, **21b**, and **21c** were separately methylated by using methyl iodide to generate the corresponding dimethoxy derivative **22a-c** (Scheme 7).

Compounds **22a-c** were subjected to RCM with G-I catalyst to give the corresponding cyclized products **23a-c**. Further, hydrogenation of unsaturated cyclophane derivatives **23a-c** was carried out under 1 atm. pressure of H_2 to deliver saturated derivatives **24a-c**. Interestingly, **22c** on RCM reaction gives mixture of two isomeric products, in which one isomer having both methoxy groups are *cis* to each other while the other isomer having methoxy group on opposite side. Hydrogenation of the corresponding mixture gave a single product **24c**, and its structure is supported by ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectral data (Table 1).

Reagents and conditions: (a) allyl bromide, K_2CO_3 , acetone; (b) dichlorobenzene, reflux

Scheme 7. Synthesis of substrates **21a-c** by DCR reaction.

Table 1 List of cyclophane derivatives prepared by DCR and RCM strategy

Claisen product	Methylation product	RCM product	Hydrogenated product
 24a (95%)			
 24b (94%)			
 24c (94%)			

Conclusion

We have designed simple synthetic strategies to cyclophane derivatives by TCR and RCM as key steps. In the first strategy we attempted TCR was followed by RCM was unsuccessful because RCM step was not realized to design cyclophane derivatives under different reaction conditions. In the second strategy the CR step was not realized even when we used silicon and phosphorous tethers to facilitate the RCM process. On the other hand, diverse cyclophane derivatives were successfully assembled when ethylene oxy tether was employed for connecting the two phenolic moieties. Later, double Claisen rearrangement and RCM protocol was found to be useful to design various cyclophane derivatives.

Experimental

Synthesis of compounds **2a-b** :

To a solution of 2-allyl phenol **1a** (1 g, 6.75 mmol) in dry acetone, powdered K_2CO_3 (5.58 g, 40.5 mmol) was added and stirred for 10 min. Then 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)propene-1 (830 mg, 1 mmol) was added

dropwise and refluxed for 24 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was filtered through Celite and washed with ethyl acetate (10 mL). The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 1% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave compound **2a**.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **1b** (1 g, 6.09 mmol) to generate compound **2b**.

2a : (987 mg, 84%); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.26 (6H, s), 3.37 (4H, d, J 6.4 Hz), 4.06 (4H, d, J 5.6 Hz), 5.06–4.98 (4H, m), 5.37 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 6.00–5.93 (2H, m), 6.75 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 6.95 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 20.7, 34.5, 92.0, 114.7, 115.5, 126.6, 126.9, 127.9, 129.4, 130.9, 131.7, 137.2, 152.9; HRMS (Q-ToF) m/z : $[M+H]^+$ Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{29}O_2$: 349.2170, Found : 349.2168; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 810, 912, 1017, 1117, 1208, 1413, 1499, 1638, 1684, 2922, 2972 cm^{-1} .

2b : (996 mg, 86%); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.37 (4H, d, J 6.8 Hz), 3.76 (6H, s), 4.56 (4H, s), 5.07–

5.01 (4H, m), 5.38 (2H, s), 6.01–5.91 (2H, m), 6.74–6.67 (4H, m), 6.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 34.7, 55.8, 69.6, 111.5, 112.8, 114.7, 115.8, 116.3, 130.3, 136.8, 141.3, 150.6, 153.9; HRMS (Q-Tof) *m/z* : [M+Na]⁺ Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₈O₄Na : 403.1885, Found : 403.1882; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 801, 915, 1045, 1223, 1281, 1264, 1498, 2830, 2935 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis of compounds 3a-b :

The compound **2a** (1 g, 2.87 mmol) was heated at 170 to 180 °C for 6 h in a sealed tube. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was cooled and directly charged on the column. The product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 4% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gives TCR product **3a**.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **2b** (1 g, 2.67 mmol) to generate compound **3b**.

3a : (270 mg, 27%); m.p. 96–98 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.24 (6H, s), 3.34 (4H, s), 3.37 (4H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 4.89 (2H, s), 5.09 (6H, m), 6.07–5.94 (2H, m), 6.77 (2H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz), 6.82 (2H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 20.6, 35.3, 37.8, 113.0, 116.2, 125.2, 126.0, 129.6, 129.9, 130.2, 136.9, 147.6, 150.6; HRMS (Q-Tof) *m/z* : [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₉O₂ : 349.2160, Found : 349.2170; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 801, 914, 1044, 1226, 1432, 1463, 1496, 1591, 1638, 2910, 2999, 3077 cm⁻¹.

3b : (330 mg, 33%); m.p. 90–92 °C : ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.36 (4H, s), 3.37 (4H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 3.74 (6H, s), 4.90 (4H, d, *J* 4.4 Hz), 5.11 (2H, dd, *J*₁ 5.2 Hz, *J*₂ 1.6 Hz), 5.14 (2H, s), 6.03–5.95 (2H, m), 6.55 (2H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz), 6.59 (2H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 35.5, 38.0, 55.8, 113.3, 114.3, 114.6, 116.5, 126.5, 127.4, 136.6, 146.7, 147.0, 153.6; HRMS (Q-Tof) *m/z* : [M+Na]⁺ Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₈O₄Na : 403.1985, Found : 403.1902; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 764, 907, 1051, 1177, 1197, 1351, 1479, 1599, 2925, 3483 cm⁻¹.

Boron trichloride catalyzed TCR :

To a solution of the compound **2** in dry DCM, boron trichloride (2 equiv.) was added at 0 °C and stirred at 0 °C for 5 h under nitrogen. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction was quenched with water (1 mL). The product was extracted with DCM

(50 mL) and washed with water, brine solution. The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography. Elution of the column with 5% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave the rearranged product. When the reaction was carried out with 4 equiv. of boron trichloride, the expected tandem Claisen rearranged product was formed along with cyclized product **7**.

3a R = Me, 35% + mono CR 30%

3b R = OMe, 80%

7 : (280 mg, 28%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.39 (3H, s), 2.23 (6H, s), 2.90 (1H, 1/2ABq, *J* 15.6 Hz), 3.09 and 3.03 (2H, ABq, *J* 14.6 Hz), 3.24 (1H, 1/2ABq, *J* 15.6 Hz), 3.28 (2H, t, *J* 5.6 Hz), 3.37 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 5.11–5.00 (4H, m), 6.04–5.90 (2H, m), 6.74 (2H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 6.80 (1H, s), 6.83 (1H, s), 7.40 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 20.6, 21.0, 26.5, 34.0, 34.9, 40.8, 43.2, 91.0, 115.2, 116.1, 122.0, 123.6, 123.9, 126.6, 128.3, 128.9, 129.1, 129.8, 130.8, 131.2, 136.2, 137.5, 151.3, 153.2; HRMS (Q-Tof) *m/z* : [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₉O₂ : 349.2173, Found : 349.2168; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 915, 1065, 1146, 1215, 1481, 1611, 1715, 2924, 3437 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis of compound 9 :

To a solution of compound **3b** (300 mg, 0.789 mmol) and triethyl amine (160 mg, 0.22 mL, 1.578 mmol) in toluene (20 mL), dichlorodimethylsilane (102 mg, 0.095 mL, 0.789 mmol) was added at 0 °C and the reaction mixture was stirred at rt for 7 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the triethyl amine hydrochloride salt was filtered through sintered funnel. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. The elution of column with 3% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave the silicon tethered product **9** (250 mg, 72%) as a white semi-solid.

9 : ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.31 (6H, s), 3.31 (4H, s), 3.32 (4H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 3.76 (6H, s), 4.79 (2H, s), 5.12–5.04 (4H, m), 5.99–5.91 (2H, m), 6.59 (2H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz), 6.61 (2H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.34, 35.4, 38.3, 55.7, 113.1, 113.5, 114.3, 116.5, 131.3, 132.6, 136.5, 144.7, 149.3, 154.3; HRMS (Q-Tof) *m/z* : [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₂₆H₃₃O₄Si : 437.2148, Found : 437.2152; IR (KBr) ν_{max} :

803, 936, 1055, 1150, 1222, 1440, 1468, 1606, 1639, 2836, 2936, 3077 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of compound 11 :

A solution of the compound **3b** (70 mg, 0.184 mmol), Et_3N (37 mg, 0.368 mmol) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (45 mg, 0.368 mmol) in dry DCM (10 mL) was cooled to 0 °C and phosphorus trichloride (25 mg, 0.184 mmol) was added dropwise. Then, the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 5 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude mixture was diluted with diethyl ether and water; the organic layer was separated and the water layer was again washed with diethyl ether. The combined organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of column with 10% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gives **11** (34 mg, 43%).

11 : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.50–3.32 (8H, m), 3.77 (6H, s), 4.95 (2H, s), 5.16–5.09 (4H, m), 6.00–5.93 (2H, m), 6.64 (4H, s), 7.41 (1H, d, J_{PH} 747.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 35.8, 38.0, 55.7, 114.0, 114.9, 115.3, 117.2, 132.9 (d, J_{CP} 4.0 Hz), 133.9 (d, J_{CP} 3.0 Hz), 135.7, 141.2 (d, J_{CP} 11.0 Hz), 146.9, 157.0; ^{31}P NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ -2.28; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 748, 942, 1045, 1258, 1438, 1464, 1605, 1639, 2923, 3413 cm^{-1} .

O-Acetyl-2-allyl phenols (13a-b) :

To a stirred solution of 2-allylphenol **1a** (100 mg, 0.675 mmol) and iodine (0.05 equiv.), Ac_2O (75 mg, 0.743 mmol) was added and stirred at room temperature for 10 min. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the residual iodine was removed by washing with saturated sodium thiosulfate solution. The product was extracted with diethyl ether. The combined organic layer was washed with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 (25 mL), brine (25 mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 . Then, solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 5% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave **13a** (80 mg, 63%). The products were light and air sensitive.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **1b** (100 mg, 0.675 mmol) to generate compound **13b** (108 mg, 87%).

13a : ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.28 (3H, s), 2.31 (3H, s), 3.25 (2H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 5.06 (2H, dsxt, J_1 12.8 Hz, J_2 1.8 Hz), 5.95–5.82 (1H, m), 6.90 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.03 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 21.0, 21.0, 34.7, 116.1, 122.1, 128.0, 131.0, 131.5, 135.8, 136.0, 146.7, 169.6.

13b : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.28 (3H, s), 3.26 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s), 5.11–5.04 (2H, m), 5.95–5.81 (1H, m), 6.75 (2H, m), 6.94 (1H, dd, J_1 9.6 Hz, J_2 2.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 20.9, 34.9, 55.6, 112.4, 115.6, 116.4, 123.0, 133.0, 135.7, 142.5, 157.5, 169.8.

Synthesis of compound 14a-b :

A solution of *O*-acetyl-2-allyl phenol **13a** (100 mg, 0.526 mmol) in dry DCM was degassed with nitrogen for 5 min and then, Grubbs 1st or 2nd generation catalyst (0.5 mmol%) was added and then, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 72 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 10% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave the cross-metathesis product **14a** (68 mg, 74%) as white solids.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **13b** (100 mg, 0.485 mmol) to generate compound **14b** (76 mg, 82%).

14a : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.23 (6H, s), 2.31 (6H, s), 3.21 (4H, dd, J_1 3.7 Hz, J_2 1.5 Hz), 5.56 (2H, m), 6.90 (2H, d, J 7.9 Hz), 7.03 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 20.97, 21.03, 33.5, 122.1, 128.0, 129.4, 131.0, 132.1, 135.9, 146.7, 169.8; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4$: 353.1753, Found : 353.1753; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 741, 1195, 1266, 1422, 1498, 1758, 2987, 3055 cm^{-1} .

14b : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.24 (6H, s), 3.22 (4H, t, J_1 3.6 Hz, J_2 1.2 Hz), 3.77 (6H, s), 5.57 (2H, m), 6.75 (4H, m), 6.93 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 20.9, 33.6, 55.6, 112.4, 115.5, 123.0, 129.4, 133.5, 142.5, 157.5, 169.9; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_6$: 385.1651, Found : 385.1651; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 824, 899, 1038, 1109, 1182, 1275, 1492, 1745, 2839, 2942, 3447 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of compound 15a-b :

To a solution of **14a** (100 mg, 0.284 mmol) in dry

ethyl acetate, 5% palladium/charcoal (10 mol%) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred under 1 atm. hydrogen pressure for 24 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was filtered through Celite and washed with ethyl acetate (2–3 times). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product was purified by column chromatography. Elution of the column with 10% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gives hydrogenated product **15a** (99 mg, 99%) as white solids.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **14b** (100 mg, 0.260 mmol) to generate compound **15b** (94 mg, 94%).

15a : ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.6 (4H, m), 2.27 (6H, s), 2.30 (6H, s), 2.48 (4H, m), 6.89 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.99 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 20.96, 21.03, 29.8, 30.1, 122.0, 127.7, 130.9, 133.8, 135.7, 146.8, 169.8; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4$: 355.1909, Found : 355.1924; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 825, 903, 1011, 1192, 1218, 1369, 1497, 1760, 2862, 2931 cm^{-1} .

15b : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.60 (4H, m), 2.27 (6H, s), 2.50 (4H, m), 3.78 (6H, s), 6.74 (4H, m), 6.93 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 21.0, 29.6, 30.3, 55.6, 111.9, 115.5, 123.0, 135.5, 142.6, 157.5, 170.1; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_6$: 387.1808, Found : 387.1808; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 820, 890, 1037, 1196, 1221, 1281, 1493, 1591, 1749, 2859, 2949 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of compound **16a-b** :

To a solution of compound **15a** (100 mg, 0.282 mmol) in dry methanol, powdered K_2CO_3 (155 mg, 1.128 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the solvent was evaporated under vacuum and the residue was neutralized with 1 *N* hydrochloric acid and extracted with diethyl ether (2–3 times). The combined organic layer was washed with water, brine, dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 15% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave deacetylated product **16a** (67 mg, 89%) as white solids.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **15b**

(100 mg, 0.259 mmol) to generate compound **16b** (60 mg, 77%).

16a : m.p. 160–162 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, MeOD) : δ 1.6 (4H, m), 2.19 (6H, s), 2.56 (4H, m), 6.60 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.76 (2H, dd, J_1 8.0 Hz, J_2 1.8 Hz), 6.84 (2H, d, J 1.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, MeOD) : δ 20.7, 31.1, 31.1, 115.8, 128.0, 129.5, 130.1, 131.7, 153.8; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2$: 271.1698, Found : 271.1697; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 801, 1037, 1207, 1283, 1440, 1455, 1509, 1600, 2859, 2944, 3292 cm^{-1} .

16b : m.p. 170–172 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, MeOD) : δ 1.62 (4H, m), 2.59 (4H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 3.69 (6H, s), 6.55 (2H, dd, J_1 8.4 Hz, J_2 3.0 Hz), 6.66–6.63 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, MeOD) : δ 30.9, 31.3, 56.2, 112.7, 116.6, 116.9, 131.5, 150.1, 154.4; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4$: 303.1596, Found : 303.1600; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 801, 1037, 1208, 1351, 1456, 1510, 1599, 2945, 3407 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of compound **17a-b** :

To a suspension of NaH (4 equiv.; washed with dry pet ether 2–3 times) in DMF (10 mL), compound **16a** (50 mg, 0.185 mmol) was added and then, the reaction mixture was cooled to 0 °C and 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)propene-1 (1 equiv.) was added dropwise and stirred for 24 h at rt. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated NH_4Cl solution, extracted with ethyl acetate, washed with water, brine and dried over Na_2SO_4 . The product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 2% ethyl acetate/petroleum ether gave **17a** (22 mg, 37%) as white solids.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **16b** (50 mg, 0.165 mmol) to generate compound **17b** (30 mg, 26%).

17a : m.p. 115–118 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.61 (4H, s), 2.25 (6H, s), 2.74 (4H, m), 4.56 (4H, s), 5.44 (2H, s), 6.76 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 6.89 (2H, m), 6.97 (2H, d, J 2.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 20.7, 27.9, 30.6, 72.1, 112.4, 120.2, 127.1, 130.4, 131.6, 132.6, 141.8, 154.9; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_2$: 323.2011, Found : 323.2011; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 799, 1033, 1235, 1251, 1351, 1379, 1502, 1600, 2856, 2921 cm^{-1} .

17b : m.p. 130–134 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz,

CDCl_3) : δ 1.62 (4H, m), 2.76 (4H, m), 3.75 (6H, s), 4.55 (4H, s), 5.43 (2H, s), 6.64 (2H, dd, J_1 8.8 Hz, J_2 3.2 Hz), 6.74 (2H, d, J 3.2 Hz), 6.81 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 27.9, 30.4, 55.7, 72.3, 111.1, 114.0, 116.6, 119.0, 134.1, 142.2, 151.1, 154.2; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4$: 355.1909, Found : 355.1897; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 786, 1035, 1245, 1505, 1565, 2849, 2904 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of compound 18 :

To a solution of compound **17b** (50 mg, 0.141 mmol) in dry DCM (10 mL), boron trichloride (2 equiv.) was added at 0 °C and stirred at 0 °C for 5 h under nitrogen. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction was quenched with water. The product was extracted with DCM and washed with water, brine solution. The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under vacuum. The product was purified by column chromatography. Elution of the column with 5% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether gave the unexpected product **18** (23 mg, 63%).

18 : m.p. 122–126 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.66 (4H, m), 2.65 (4H, m), 3.41 (2H, s), 3.70 (6H, s), 4.00 (2H, s), 4.90 (2H, bs), 4.91 (1H, s), 5.16 (1H, s), 6.63–6.59 (3H, m), 6.72–6.68 (2H, dd, J_1 8.8 Hz, J_2 3.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 29.6, 29.7, 29.7, 29.8, 33.4, 48.1, 55.9, 56.4, 111.9, 113.3, 115.9, 116.1, 116.2, 117.8, 125.8, 127.4, 129.8, 144.3, 147.1, 147.5, 152.0, 153.9; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$: 391.1676, Found : 391.1687; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 770, 1023, 1209, 1351, 1595, 2930, 3427 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for O-allylation :

To a stirred solution of bisphenol **19** (334 mg, 1 mmol) in acetone (15 mL) was added K_2CO_3 (5 mmol) and the resultant suspension was stirred for 30 min. Then, allyl bromide (3 mmol) was added dropwise into the reaction mixture over a period of 10 min. Further, the reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h at reflux. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the crude mixture was filtered through Celite pad (washed with CH_2Cl_2) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica-gel, 5% EtOAc-petroleum ether).

(Compound **20** data has been reported in reference no. 5)

20 : (372 mg, yield : 90%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.74 (4H, s), 3.85 (4H, t, J 4.4 Hz), 4.10 (4H, t, J 4.4 Hz), 4.49 (4H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 5.25–5.41 (4H, m), 5.99–6.08 (2H, m), 6.47–6.54 (6H, m), 7.14 (2H, t, J 8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 67.5, 68.9, 69.9, 71.0, 102.0, 107.1, 107.4, 117.8, 129.9, 133.4, 159.9, 160.1; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{K}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{K}$: 453.1671, Found : 453.1674; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 740, 1265, 1453, 1598, 2873, 3054 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for Claisen rearrangement :

Product obtained by allylation **20** (414 mg, 1 mmol) was dissolved in dichlorobenzene (10 mL) and the reaction mixture was heated at reflux for a period of 24 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), reaction mixture was cooled. The crude reaction mixture was directly subjected to column chromatography. Dichlorobenzene was removed by elution with petroleum ether. Further elution of column was achieved by using petroleum ether/ethyl acetate mixture.

(Compound **21a** data has been reported in reference no. 5)

21b : (83 mg, yield : 20%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.32 (2H, bd, J 6.0 Hz), 3.46 (2H, bd, J 6.0 Hz), 3.84 (4H, s), 3.71–3.90 (4H, m), 4.04–4.14 (4H, m), 5.03–5.14 (4H, m), 5.21 (1H, s), 5.38 (1H, s), 5.91–6.03 (2H, m), 6.40–6.50 (4H, m), 6.95 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.03 (1H, t, J 8.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 27.7, 34.5, 67.5, 68.3, 69.9, 70.0, 70.9, 71.0, 102.9, 104.7, 106.9, 109.2, 114.3, 115.5, 116.2, 117.9, 127.6, 130.8, 136.6, 137.0, 155.1, 155.3, 157.5, 158.7; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 437.1935, Found : 437.1935; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 740, 1265, 1453, 1598, 2873, 2985, 3696 cm^{-1} .

21c : (91 mg, yield : 22%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.33 (4H, d, J 6.3 Hz), 3.73 (4H, s), 3.82 (4H, t, J 3.6 Hz), 4.07 (4H, t, J 4.3 Hz), 5.09–5.14 (4H, m), 5.44 (2H, s), 5.93–6.03 (2H, m), 6.42–6.44 (4H, m), 6.96 (2H, d, J 7.9 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 34.5, 67.6, 69.9, 70.9, 103.0, 106.9, 116.1, 118.1, 130.8, 137.1, 155.1, 158.7; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 437.1935, Found : 437.1933; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 740, 1265, 1422, 1594, 3428 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for methylation of phenol derivatives :

To a stirred solution of Claisen rearrangement prod-

uct **21b** (414 mg, 1 mmol) dissolved in acetone (15 mL), K_2CO_3 (5 mmol) was added and the resultant suspension was stirred for 30 min. Then MeI (10 mmol) was added and reaction mixture was further stirred for 6 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the crude mixture was filtered through Celite pad (washed with CH_2Cl_2) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica-gel, 5% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to afford **22b**.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **21c** (414 mg, 1 mmol) to generate compound **22c** (411 mg, yield : 93%).

22b : (397 mg, yield : 90%); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.30 (2H, dt, J_1 1.6 Hz, J_2 6.5 Hz), 3.42 (2H, dt, J_1 1.51 Hz, J_2 6.2 Hz), 3.72–3.77 (4H, m), 3.78 (3H, s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.85–3.89 (4H, m), 4.09–4.14 (4H, m), 4.98–5.04 (4H, m), 5.88–6.02 (2H, m), 6.42 (1H, dd, J_1 2.51 Hz, J_2 8.2 Hz), 6.49 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 6.51–6.56 (2H, m), 7.00 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.11 (1H, t, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 27.5, 33.7, 55.5, 55.5, 55.9, 56.0, 67.6, 68.3, 70.0, 70.1, 71.0, 71.1, 99.4, 104.2, 104.8, 105.2, 114.2, 115.1, 121.3, 127.2, 130.0, 137.1, 137.5, 157.5, 158.4, 158.7; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[M+Na]^+$ Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{34}O_6Na$: 465.2248, Found : 465.2244; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 745, 1265, 1472, 1595, 2938, 3054 cm^{-1} .

22c : (411 mg, yield : 93%); 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.32 (4H, d, J 6.41 Hz), 3.78 (4H, s), 3.80 (6H, s), 3.86–3.90 (4H, m), 4.12–4.16 (4H, m), 5.01–5.06 (4H, m), 5.99 (2H, ddt, J_1 6.64 Hz, J_2 10.3 Hz, J_3 16.67 Hz), 6.45 (2H, dd, J_1 2.4 Hz, J_2 8.24 Hz), 6.51 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 7.02 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125.75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 33.7, 55.5, 67.6, 70.0, 71.0, 99.4, 104.8, 115.1, 121.3, 130.0, 137.5, 158.2, 158.6; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[M+Na]^+$ Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{34}O_6Na$: 465.2248, Found : 465.2245; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 749, 763, 1266, 1431, 1611 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for RCM :

Product obtained by methylation **22b** (398 mg, 1 mmol) was dissolved in dry toluene (10 mL) and degassed with nitrogen for 15 min. Then, Grubbs first generation catalyst (5 mol%) was added and reaction mixture was refluxed overnight. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the crude mixture was filtered through Celite

pad (washed with CH_2Cl_2) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica-gel/ EtOAc-petroleum ether) to afford the cyclophane derivative **23b**. Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **22c** (398 mg, 1 mmol) to generate compound **23c** (264 mg, yield : 64%).

23b : (240 mg, yield : 58%); 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.20 (2H, d, J 4.1 Hz), 3.34 (2H, d, J 4.2 Hz), 3.40 (2H, t, J 3.1 Hz), 3.41–3.50 (4H, m), 3.56–3.60 (2H, m), 3.70 (4H, s), 3.80 (6H, s), 5.40 (2H, m), 6.41–6.60 (4H, m), 6.90 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.13 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (125.75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 26.3, 32.1, 55.5, 56.1, 67.6, 68.0, 69.5, 70.5, 71.0, 71.3, 100.4, 104.4, 106.0, 106.5, 118.2, 122.2, 127.0, 128.1, 128.9, 129.1, 130.3, 131.0, 158.0, 158.1; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[M+H]^+$ Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{31}O_6$: 415.2117, Found : 415.2115; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 740, 896, 1265, 1422, 1498, 2987, 3054 cm^{-1} .

23c : (Mixture of 2 regioisomer) (2 : 1) (264 mg, yield : 64%);

Data for 1st isomer – 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.18 (4H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 3.71 (6H, s), 3.71 (4H, s), 3.74 (4H, t, J 4.8 Hz), 4.22 (4H, t, J 4.9 Hz), 5.58–5.60 (2H, m), 6.40–6.42 (4H, m), 6.69 (2H, dd, J_1 2.0 Hz, J_2 8.0 Hz);

Data for 2nd isomer – 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.33 (4H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 3.60 (6H, s), 3.77 (4H, s), 3.78 (4H, t, J 4.8 Hz), 4.08 (4H, t, J 4.9 Hz), 5.90 (2H, t, J 1.8 Hz), 6.12 (2H, dd, J_1 2.1 Hz, J_2 8.1 Hz), 6.40 (2H, s), 6.40–6.42 (2H, m).

^{13}C NMR (125.75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 26.7, 31.1, 55.3, 55.4, 68.2, 68.4, 70.1, 70.3, 71.1, 71.3, 99.1, 100.1, 104.6, 105.6, 122.0, 123.7, 129.6, 129.7, 129.7, 130.8, 157.7, 157.8, 158.1, 158.3; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[M+Na]^+$ Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{30}O_6Na$: 437.1935, Found : 437.1937; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 742, 1265, 1421, 1451, 1610, 2932, 3054 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for hydrogenation :

RCM product obtained **23b** (207 mg, 1 mmol) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (10 mL) and 5% Pd/C was added. Further, reaction mixture was stirred at rt under hydrogen atmosphere (1 atm.) for 12 h. After the completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the crude mixture was filtered through Celite pad and the solvent was evapo-

rated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 10% (ethyl acetate/petroleum ether) gave the hydrogenated products **24b**.

Similar procedure was followed with the substrate **23c** (207 mg, 1 mmol) to generate compound **24c** (195 mg, yield : 94%).

24b : (195 mg, yield : 94%); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.57 (4H, bs), 2.66 (4H, bs), 3.40 (2H, t, J 3.8 Hz), 3.42 (2H, t, J 3.8 Hz), 3.48–3.50 (2H, m), 3.51–3.52 (2H, m), 3.82 (4H, s), 3.90–3.99 (6H, m), 6.50 (4H, dd, J_1 2.2 Hz, J_2 8.3 Hz), 6.60–6.99 (1H, m), 7.08 (1H, t, J 3.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 26.3, 32.1, 67.6, 68.0, 69.5, 70.5, 71.0, 71.3, 100.4, 104.4, 106.0, 106.5, 118.2, 122.2, 127.0, 128.1, 130.3, 131.0, 158.0, 158.1; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 439.2091, Found : 439.2093; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 747, 1266, 1453, 1506, 2925, 3402 cm^{-1} .

24c : (195 mg, yield : 94%); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.52 (4H, bs), 2.43 (4H, bs), 3.65 (6H, s), 3.71 (4H, s), 3.80–3.83 (4H, m), 4.16–4.19 (4H, m), 6.28–6.33 (4H, m), 6.49 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125.75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 28.3, 29.8, 55.2, 68.2, 70.1, 71.3, 99.6, 104.7, 123.1, 130.0, 158.1, 158.4; HRMS (Q-Tof) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 439.2090, Found : 439.2093; IR (neat) ν_{max} : 747, 1264, 1450, 1506, 2926, 3412 cm^{-1} .

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